

On the Sequential Composition of the Moore-Penrose Matrix Inverse

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1 Some Preliminary Results

Definition 1 (The Correction Function). *Define the correction function as the following lambda abstraction:*

$$\lambda x, y, u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2. ((x^\dagger \ u_2 \ u_1), (v_2 \ v_1 \ y^\dagger))$$

From now on, we refer to this function as:

$$\delta(x, y) = \lambda u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2. ((x^\dagger \ u_2 \ u_1), (v_2 \ v_1 \ y^\dagger))$$

Based on this correction function, we define an abstraction triple as follows:

Definition 2 (An Abstraction Triple). *Given a Moore-Penrose abstraction pair, (α, α^\dagger) , an abstraction triple is defined as the triple, $(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha))$.*

Now, define the *corrected sequential composition* of two correction abstraction triples as follows.

Definition 3 (Corrected Sequential Composition). *Given two corrected abstraction triples, $(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha))$ and $(\beta, \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, \beta))$, then the corrected sequential composition, $\dot{+}$, is defined as follows:*

$$(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (\beta, \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, \beta)) = (\alpha\beta, \beta^\dagger\alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \beta))$$

Such that the following conditions apply,

1- $(\alpha\beta)(\delta(\alpha, \beta)(\beta^\dagger\alpha^\dagger\beta^\dagger\alpha^\dagger)) = \pi_{\beta^\dagger\alpha^\dagger}$ and,

2- $(\beta^\dagger\alpha^\dagger)(\delta(\alpha, \beta)(\alpha\beta\alpha\beta)) = \pi_{\alpha\beta}$

In fact, it is straightforward to demonstrate that

$$(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (I, I^\dagger, \delta(I, I)) = (\alpha I, I^\dagger\alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, I))$$

has the property,

$$\delta(\alpha, I)(I^\dagger\alpha^\dagger I^\dagger\alpha^\dagger) = \alpha^\dagger$$

and symmetrically,

$$\delta(\alpha, I)(\alpha I \alpha I) = \alpha$$

This promotes the philosophy that an abstraction triple is a more general concept compared to the Moore-Penrose pair. This is specially shown by defining the set of *sequentially-composed* abstraction triples:

$$\mathcal{S} = \{(v, v^\dagger, \delta(v, v)) \dot{+} (v', v'^\dagger, \delta(v', v')) \mid v, v' \in \mathcal{V}\}$$

where \mathcal{V} is the set of all abstractions including the identity abstraction, I , and $\delta(x, y)$ is the correction function. Then, it is possible to use \mathcal{S} as the domain of meaning for Moore-Penrose pairs. This is done by first defining a translation function, \mathcal{T} , as follows:

$$\mathcal{T}[(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger)] = (\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (I, I^\dagger, \delta(I, I)) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{T}[(\alpha\beta, \beta^\dagger\alpha^\dagger)] = (\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (\beta, \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, \beta)) \quad (2)$$

And then working over the new set, \mathcal{S} . Note now that the smallest abstraction unit in \mathcal{S} is the corrected sequential composition of at least two abstraction triples.

For example, let us consider the composition of the translation of two Moore-Penrose pairs, $\mathcal{T}[(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger)] \dot{+} \mathcal{T}[(\beta, \beta^\dagger)]$, in the set of \mathcal{S} . First we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}[(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger)] &= (\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (I, I^\dagger, \delta(I, I)), \text{ and} \\ \mathcal{T}[(\beta, \beta^\dagger)] &= (\beta, \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, \beta)) \dot{+} (I, I^\dagger, \delta(I, I)) \end{aligned}$$

From which we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} &((\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (I, I^\dagger, \delta(I, I))) \dot{+} ((\beta, \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, \beta)) \dot{+} (I, I^\dagger, \delta(I, I))) = \\ &(\alpha I, I^\dagger \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, I)) \dot{+} (\beta I, I^\dagger \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, I)) = \\ &(\alpha I \beta I, I^\dagger \beta^\dagger I^\dagger \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha I, \beta I)) = \\ &(\alpha\beta, \beta^\dagger \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \beta)) = \\ &(\alpha, \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \alpha)) \dot{+} (\beta, \beta^\dagger, \delta(\beta, \beta)) = \\ &\mathcal{T}[(\alpha\beta, \beta^\dagger \alpha^\dagger)] \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, it is possible to demonstrate that:

$$\begin{aligned} &((\alpha\beta, \beta^\dagger \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha, \beta)) \dot{+} (\gamma\zeta, \zeta^\dagger \gamma^\dagger, \delta(\gamma, \zeta))) = \\ &((\alpha\beta\gamma\zeta, \zeta^\dagger \gamma^\dagger \beta^\dagger \alpha^\dagger, \delta(\alpha\beta, \gamma\zeta))) \end{aligned}$$

This promotes compositionality!